

DEVELOPMENT OF GREENER AND MORE EFFECTIVE HIGH-TEMPERATURE THERMAL INSULATORS

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Abstract

Aiming at reducing the remarkable shrinkage observed when porous ceramics are fired, the *in-situ* formation of hibonite (also known as $\text{CaO}\cdot 6\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ or CA_6) was evaluated in a direct-foamed alumina-based macroporous thermal insulator with the addition of distinct calcium sources and contents. Among the tested compositions, that containing 12.9 wt% of CaCO_3 showed promising results as high porosity (~ 80 %), no shrinkage after firing at 1600 °C for 5 h, suitable mechanical strength, and a 200 °C-lower strengthening temperature. However, the *in-situ* formation of CA_6 took place just at high temperatures (~ 1600 °C), implying a high energy consumption. To address this issue, SiO_2 , ZnO , and TiO_2 were evaluated as mineralizing agents. The addition of 2.8 mol% of TiO_2 induced CA_6 formation at 1300°C and low thermal conductivity ($0.54 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ at 1200 °C), without significant changes in the refractoriness.

Introduction

Since mankind started to control and apply fire to make our world more suited to their lifestyle, which happened about one million years ago, the use of energy became to be closely related to the quality of life. A simple example of it is that an average citizen from North America spends close to 7 tons of oil-equivalent energy every year, meanwhile, a Brazilian uses one-fourth of it¹. Considering that the global economy is forecast to grow by 3 % per year until 2040² and that economic

prosperity leads to life quality increases, we will face a future of high power requirements. In fact, according to the U.S. Energy Information Administration, the global energy demand will rise by 47 % until 2050³. Therefore, the easiest pathway to supply such growing requirements, ensuring energy security and environmental protection, is by increasing energy efficiency.

Accounting for 37 % of all power consumed in the world, industries play a key role when energetic issues are under discussion⁴. In this scenario, macroporous refractory ceramics have been drawing attention as they can be used as thermal insulators, reducing the amount of energy spent and decreasing production costs. However, to replace the commonly used fiber-based insulators (which can be highly toxic when inhaled and present a shorter working life span) for macroporous materials, some challenges should be overcome. Among them, the control of shrinkage after firing, the reduction of thermal conductivity, and the decrease of the energy input required to manufacture this type of material, can be quoted.

To address these challenges, ceramic systems able to react at high temperatures forming expansive, refractory and low thermal conductivity phases are desirable. A promising possibility is the *in-situ* formation of hibonite (also known as calcium hexaluminate, $\text{CaO}\cdot 6\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, or just CA_6). When obtained by the reaction of CaO and Al_2O_3 , this phase undergoes a volumetric expansion of approximately 16 %⁵. Thus, this expansive

effect due to CA_6 formation could counteract the material shrinkage. Furthermore, CA_6 presents high refractoriness (~ 1800 °C), low thermal conductivity and can be obtained in equiaxial or acicular morphology⁵.

However, distinct Ca^{2+} sources could be used to *in-situ* produce CA_6 , such as calcined calcium oxide, calcium carbonate, calcium hydroxide and calcium aluminate cement. Therefore, these raw materials were used in distinct contents, together with alumina, to produce macroporous ceramics by direct foaming method, applying a non-toxic surfactant agent as the bubble stabilizer. Furthermore, as CA_6 formation took place just at high temperatures (~ 1600 °C), implying a high energy consumption, SiO_2 , ZnO , and TiO_2 were evaluated as mineralizing agents.

Materials and Methods

Macroporous samples were produced using a standard composition (see Table I) and a direct foaming method⁶, which consisted of incorporating a previously prepared surfactant-based foam into an alumina suspension, as described elsewhere⁷⁻⁹. For that, Aluminas CL370 and CT3000SG (Almatis, Germany), dispersive agent Castament® FS 60 (BASF, Germany), commercial non-ionic surfactant (Lutensol® AT 50 Pulver, BASF, Germany), a commercial surfactant (Vinapor GYP 2680, BASF, Germany), and a thickening agent (Cellosize 100 CG FF, Dow Chemical, USA) were used. As Ca^{+2} sources, calcium carbonate ($CaCO_3$, Imerys, France, 99 % purity, $D_{50} = 7.38$ μm), calcium hydroxide ($Ca(OH)_2$, Synth, Brazil, 99.9 % purity, $D_{50} = 5.66$ μm), calcium oxide (CaO , $D_{50} = 14.56$ μm , obtained by calcination of calcium carbonate at 900 °C for 4 hours), and calcium aluminate cement (S71, Secar 71, Imerys Aluminates, France) were employed. Additionally, 1 wt% of hydratable alumina (Alphabond 300, Almatis, Germany) was used as binder in the reference composition (REF). The amount of each additive is depicted

in Table II. It is worth noticing that the prefix of each composition's name refers to the amount of CA_6 formed when the thermodynamic equilibrium is attained.

Table I: Basic composition for the ceramic foam.

Ceramic foam composition		
	Raw materials	wt%
Al₂O₃ Suspension	Alumina CL370	76.06
	Alumina CT3000SG	5.72
	Dispersant FS60	0.09
	Lutensol AT50	0.10
	Deionized water	15.79
Foam	Vinapor GYP 2680	3.468
	Cellosize 100CGFF	0.0056

Table II: Amount of each calcium source used.

		Calcium source (wt%)			
		Secar 71	CaCO ₃	Ca(OH) ₂	CaO
Composition	REF.	-	-	-	-
	20_S71	5.00	-	-	-
	20_CAC _L	5.00	-	-	-
	20_CaCO ₃ /S71	1.00	2.04	-	-
	20_Ca(OH) ₂ /S71	1.00	-	1.55	-
	20_CaO	-	-	-	1.42
	40_CaCO ₃ /S71	1.00	4.55	-	-
	40_Ca(OH) ₂ /S71	1.00	-	2.60	-
	40_CaO	-	-	-	2.82
	80_CaCO ₃ /S71	1.00	10.02	-	-
	80_Ca(OH) ₂ /S71	1.00	-	5.72	-
	80_CaO	-	-	-	5.86
	100_CaCO ₃ /S71	1.00	12.90	-	-

Additionally, to evaluate the effect of mineralizing agents, ZnO (PA, $D_{50} = 0.8$ μm , Synth, Diadema, Brazil), SiO_2 (Microsilica® 971-U, Elkem, Oslo, Norway) or TiO_2 (Aeroxide® P90, Evonik, Essen, Germany) was added to composition 100_CaCO₃/S71 in the range of 0.6 to 2.8 mol% of the metallic ion

in relation to the CA_6 expected to be formed (check the corresponding wt% in ⁹)

All compositions were cured at 50 °C for 24 h, dried at 110 °C for another 24 h, and fired at 1600 °C for 5 h (1 °C.min⁻¹, Lindberg Blue, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Their linear shrinkage after firing was assessed by pachymeter (model 530-104, Mitutoyo, Japan) measurements. Total porosity was calculated using the relationship between the porous sample density (liquid immersion method, based on the Archimedes' principle, according to ASTM C20) and the density of the solid fraction measured by helium pycnometry (AccuPyc 1330, Micromeritics, USA) of the powder obtained by grinding the samples. Cold crushing strength was carried out in MTS 810 equipment (MTS, USA), according to ASTM C133. The mineralogical phase content of each composition after firing was analyzed applying the Rietveld refinement method (software Topas, Bruker, USA) based on X-ray diffractograms (D8 Advance ECO with SSD160 detector, Bruker, USA). Sinterability was *in-situ* monitored by tracking the elastic modulus versus temperature profile up to 1400 °C using Scanelastic equipment (ATCP Physical engineering, Brazil), according to ASTM E1875. Some selected compositions had their microstructure assessed by scanning electron microscopy (XL-30 FEG, Philips, Nederland), and thermal conductivity as a function of temperature up to 1200 °C evaluated by the parallel hot wire technique (according to ASTM C1113), in TCT 426 equipment (Netzch, Germany).

Results and discussions

Firstly, analyzing the effect of each Ca^{2+} source, compositions REF, 20_S71, 20_CaCO₃/S71, 20_Ca(OH)₂/S71, and 20_CaO were characterized by their linear shrinkage after firing and total porosity [Fig. 1 (a)]. All compositions presented total green

porosity above 75%, highlighting the effectiveness of using a direct foaming method with an organic surfactant to produce high-porosity macroporous insulators. Composition REF underwent the highest linear shrinkage and porosity decrease after firing at 1600 °C for 5 h among all tested compositions, which is assigned to the absence of CA_6 formation after the thermal treatment. Thus, *in-situ* hibonite formation was effective in partially counteracting the material shrinkage. The shrinkage values of the calcium-containing compositions were not statistically distinct, indicating that the amount of CA_6 formed in these compositions was equivalent.

To evaluate if the same phenomenon reported by Luz *et al.* [10] (in which some calcium sources induced lower strengthening temperature in refractory castables) will be seen in the macroporous systems, these samples were evaluated by measuring their elastic modulus as a function of temperature during the firing process from room temperature up to 1400 °C [Fig. 1 (b)]. The effect of some Ca^{2+} sources on the strengthening temperature (T_s) stood out. For compositions REF and 20_S71, T_s was in the range of 900 °C and 915 °C, whereas using of other Ca^{2+} sources decreased this value to ~690 °C. These results indicated that calcium aluminate cement does not reduce the strengthening temperature. On the other hand, calcium carbonate, calcium hydroxide and calcium oxide were able to decrease this temperature close to 700°C, which are in tune with the results presented by Consoni *et al.* for dense alumina-based refractory systems ¹⁰. Although the mechanism that leads to this lower strengthen temperature is not fully established, Borges *et al.*¹¹ proposed that the formation of a hydrated phase [hydrocalumite, Ca₄Al₂(OH)₁₂(CO₃,OH)₂·4H₂O] plays a key role. According to their findings, hydrocalumite-like phases, generated on the particles' surface during the processing stage, decompose at 600 °C forming lime and highly

reactive mayenite ($12\text{CaO}\cdot 7\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$). This latter phase, located on some particles' interfaces, could react close to $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ linking them and resulting in strengthening without shrinkage.

This lower T_S value is of great interest as (i) macroporous insulators could be thermally treated at lower temperatures, just to acquire enough mechanical strength for transportation and installation, *in-situ* finishing their firing process; and (ii) lower sintering temperatures can be used to produce macroporous ceramics that would be applied in low thermal demand environments, *e.g.* aluminum industry. In both situations, the energy input required to produce the macroporous material would be reduced.

Figure 1: (a) linear shrinkage, (a) total porosity, and (b) modulus of Young evaluation, all for compositions containing distinct Ca^{2+} sources.

Facing these promising results, compositions containing even more Ca^{2+} from CaCO_3 , Ca(OH)_2 , and CaO were evaluated according to the same methods. Although mechanical strength and T_S did not change significantly (results not presented here), porosity and shrinkage values did, as shown in Figure 2 (a). It was possible to see that the increase of Ca^{2+} content induced remarkably reductions of linear shrinkage, which reached an expansion of $\sim 1\%$ for composition 100_ CaCO_3 /S71. This behavior highlights the effectiveness of *in-situ* formation of CA_6 to counteract the densification-driven shrinkage of the ceramic foam. On the other hand, the production of compositions 100_ CaO and 100_ Ca(OH)_2 /S71 was not feasible due to the effect of these calcium sources on the foam rheology, resulting in a material with low porosity ($< 50\%$). Therefore, as it was the most promising system at this point, composition 100_ CaCO_3 /S71 was evaluated according to its thermal conductivity (k_{eff}) at temperatures ranging from $40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [Figure 2 (b)].

Comparing 100_ CaCO_3 /S71 to a commercial alumino-silicate fiber-based thermal insulator, one can see that the macroporous composition showed higher k_{eff} at low temperatures ($< 1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Nevertheless, because the fiber-based insulator has a microstructure that is not effective to interact with the thermal radiation emitted at high temperatures, it underwent a pronounced increase of k_{eff} . Thus, above $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, composition 100_ CaCO_3 /S71 presented lower thermal conductivity than the fiber-based material, thus, its use is expected to reduce the energy required to operate processes working above this temperature.

Figure 2: (a) linear shrinkage and total porosity as a function of Ca²⁺ source and content; and (b) thermal conductivity (k_{eff}) of 100_CaCO₃/S71 and an alumino-silicate fiber mat up to 1200 °C.

The results discussed so far made it possible to produce a macroporous insulator that can be thermally treated at lower temperatures, presents low k_{eff} and slightly expands after firing at 1600 °C for 5 h. However, because the two latter rely on the CA₆ formation, which completely occurs in the analyzed systems close to 1600 °C, these 3 features cannot be achieved simultaneously. A way to address this issue is by reducing the temperature of CA₆ formation, which could be carried out by using mineralizing agents¹², such as SiO₂, TiO₂, and ZnO. These oxides were added to composition 100_CaCO₃/S71 in content varying from 0.6 mol% to 2.8 mol%.

Because these additives can induce the formation of a glassy phase at lower temperatures¹², all compositions were

evaluated by their refractoriness under load (RUL) (Figure 3). SiO₂ additions resulted in a higher loss of refractoriness, whereas TiO₂ and ZnO affected it much less. Considering that the macroporous thermal insulators are generally applied at high temperatures, the use of SiO₂ seems unsuitable to produce materials that can withstand these conditions without remarkable dimensional changes.

Figure 3: Refractoriness under load of composition 100_CaCO₃/S71 containing distinct amounts of SiO₂, TiO₂, or ZnO.

Therefore, the compositions containing ZnO and TiO₂ as mineralizing agents were fired at distinct temperatures for 5 h, and the CA₆ content was measured by quantitative X-ray diffraction [Figure 4 (a-b)]. The thermal treatment at 1200 °C was not enough to generate CA₆ in all tested compositions. However, at 1300 °C for TiO₂-containing compositions, and 1400 °C for those containing ZnO, more CA₆ was formed compared to composition 100_CaCO₃/S71, pointing out the mineralizing effect of these two additives. Additionally, the increase in ZnO or TiO₂ content resulted in a higher fraction of CA₆ formed. In this regard, hibonite formation was completed at 1400 °C and 1300 °C for 2.8 mol% of ZnO and TiO₂, respectively, which may allow significant reductions in the energy input required to produce these materials.

Figure 4: CA_6 content vs. firing temperature for compositions containing distinct amounts of (a) ZnO and (b) TiO_2 as mineralizing agents. The samples were held at the indicated temperature for 5 h.

Finally, to evaluate the efficiency of the macroporous thermal insulators containing 2.8 mol% of TiO_2 or ZnO, their k_{eff} were measured [Figure 5(a)]. Compared to 100_ $CaCO_3/S71$, these compositions presented lower k_{eff} for all tested temperatures, which can be assigned to the formation of highly asymmetric CA_6 that leads to the generation of more porosity due to its poor packing. Scanning electron microscopy confirmed this feature [Figure 5 (b-d)]. Additionally, despite both doped compositions had similar thermal conductivity up to 800°C, the Ti-containing showed lower k_{eff} above this temperature, which can be attributed to the opacifying effect played by TiO_2 on the thermal radiation emitted at high temperatures⁹.

Figure 5: (a) k_{eff} of compositions containing 2.8 mol% of TiO_2 or ZnO (evaluated as mineralizing agents) and composition 100_ $CaCO_3/S71$; (b-d) SEM of the same compositions.

Conclusion

The effects of adding distinct Ca^{2+} sources in alumina-based macroporous insulators produced by a direct foaming method were evaluated. CaCO_3 , $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, and CaO induced reductions on the onset strengthening temperature (T_s), which was not detected when calcium aluminate cement or hydratable alumina were used. Therefore, the formers can be applied to lower the firing temperatures used in the production of macroporous materials, leading to the reduction of processing energy. Besides that, all Ca^{2+} sources tested were effective at inducing the *in-situ* formation of CA_6 after thermal treatment at 1600 °C for 5 h. Due to their impact on the system rheology, CaO and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ were not feasible to be used in higher contents as they reduced the porosity and increased the pore size. On the other hand, CaCO_3 could be added in higher concentrations, favoring the production of a composition comprising 100% of CA_6 (named 100_ CaCO_3 /S71), which presented expansion of almost 1% after firing at 1600 °C for 5h.

However, as CA_6 are completely formed close to 1600 °C in these systems, implying high energy demand, the effects of using distinct mineralizing agents (ZnO , SiO_2 , and TiO_2) were studied. Using ZnO and TiO_2 favored CA_6 generation at lower temperatures. For the higher additive content (2.8 mol%), TiO_2 and ZnO induced full CA_6 formation at 1300 °C and 1400 °C, respectively. In addition, these compositions presented high porosity (> 80 %) and refractoriness ($T_{0.5\%} > 1500$ °C), no shrinkage after firing at 1600 °C for 5 h, suitable mechanical strength, low thermal conductivity (0.54 and 0.58 $\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ at 1200 °C, respectively) and highly asymmetric CA_6 . Therefore, the application of this material as thermal insulators can increase the efficiency of high-temperature processes, lowering environmental impacts and production costs.

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Bibliography

1. IEA - International Energy Agency. Energy use (kg of oil equivalent per capita). *The World Bank* (2021). Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EG.US.E.PCAP.KG.OE>.
2. Office of the Director of National Intelligence of the United States of America. Global Trends 2040: A More Contested World. 156 (2021).
3. U.S. Energy Information Administration. The International Energy Outlook. (2021).
4. IEA. *World Energy Balances. International Energy Agency* (OECD, 2019).
5. Domínguez, C. *et al.* Microstructure development in calcium hexaluminate. *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* **21**, 381–387 (2001).
6. Salvini, V. R., Lasso, P. R. O., Luz, A. P. & Pandolfelli, V. C. Nontoxic processing of reliable macro-porous ceramics. *Int. J. Appl. Ceram. Technol.* **13**, 522–531 (2016).
7. Borges, O. H., Santos Junior, T., Oliveira, R. R. B., Salvini, V. R. & Pandolfelli, V. C. Macroporous high-temperature insulators physical properties by *in situ* CA_6 formation: does the calcium source matter? *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* **40**, 3679–3686 (2020).

8. Santos Junior, T. *et al.* Development of Al₂O₃-CAC refractory macroporous ceramics derived from ultrastable foams and CAC aqueous suspensions. in *The Unified International Technical Conference on Refractories* 1–4 (2019).
9. Borges, O. H., Santos, T., Salvini, V. R. & Pandolfelli, V. C. CA₆-based macroporous refractory thermal insulators containing mineralizing agents. *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* **40**, 6141–6148 (2020).
10. Consonni, L. B., Luz, A. P. & Pandolfelli, V. C. Binding additives with sintering action for high-alumina based castables. *Ceram. Int.* **45**, 15290–15297 (2019).
11. Borges, O. H., Santos, T., Salvini, V. R. & Pandolfelli, V. C. Al₂O₃-CaO macroporous ceramics containing hydrocalumite-like phases. *Ceram. Int.* **46**, 5929–5936 (2020).
12. Souza, T. M., Luz, A. P., Pagliosa, C. & Pandolfelli, V. C. Mineralizing alumina-magnesia cement-bonded castables containing magnesium borates. *Ceram. Int.* (2015). doi:10.1016/j.ceramint.2015.05.063